

Breaching planetary boundaries: Over half of global land area suffers critical losses in functional biosphere integrity

Graphical abstract

Authors

Fabian Stenzel, Liad Ben Uri, Johanna Braun, ..., Nicolas Roux, Sibyll Schaphoff, Wolfgang Lucht

Correspondence

stenzel@pik-potsdam.de

In brief

Over half of Earth's land surface has transgressed critical ecological thresholds, signaling a breach of the planetary boundary for functional biosphere integrity. By combining indicators of human pressure and ecosystem disruption, this study reveals locations and points in time that indicate ecological degradation. The findings stress the urgent need to safeguard ecosystems as a foundation for a stable and resilient planet.

Highlights

- Spatially and temporally explicit mapping of HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk
- Two control variables for the planetary boundary for functional biosphere integrity
- Local transgression thresholds determined from independent biosphere integrity datasets
- Boundary currently transgressed on 60% of the land area, with 38% already at high risk

Article

Breaching planetary boundaries: Over half of global land area suffers critical losses in functional biosphere integrity

Fabian Stenzel,^{1,2,8,*} Liad Ben Uri,³ Johanna Braun,¹ Jannes Breier,¹ Karlheinz Erb,⁴ Dieter Gerten,^{1,5,6} Helmut Haberl,⁴ Sarah Matej,⁴ Ron Milo,³ Sebastian Ostberg,¹ Johan Rockström,^{1,2,7} Nicolas Roux,⁴ Sibyll Schaphoff,¹ and Wolfgang Lucht^{1,5,6}

¹Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Member of the Leibniz Association, PO Box 60 12 03, D-14412 Potsdam, Germany

²Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Stockholm, Sweden

³Department of Plant and Environmental Sciences, Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot, Israel

⁴Institute of Social Ecology, Department of Economics and Social Sciences, BOKU University, Vienna, Austria

⁵Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Department of Geography, Unter den Linden 6, D-10099 Berlin, Germany

⁶Integrative Research Institute on Transformations of Human-Environment Systems, Unter den Linden 6, D-10099 Berlin, Germany

⁷Institute of Environmental Science and Geography, University of Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany

⁸Lead contact

*Correspondence: stenzel@pik-potsdam.de

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2025.101393>

SCIENCE FOR SOCIETY A stable Earth system requires a healthy biosphere, but many ecosystems are being pushed beyond safe limits due to human activities such as land-use change, resource extraction, or climatic changes. Several indicators exist to assess the local state of the biosphere. However, ones that can be aggregated globally and directly linked to planetary-scale thresholds for ecosystem integrity are still lacking, compromising our ability to mitigate degradation and deploy conservation strategies.

Our research maps two global indicators that track human pressure on ecosystems, as well as ecological disruption, which we propose for the planetary-boundaries framework to represent the boundary for functional biosphere integrity. We show that the integrity of ecosystems has already been critically compromised across large parts of the planet. These findings can inform global and local environmental governance, helping policy-makers, conservation agencies, and land-use planners to avoid further breaching of these boundaries and limiting the risk of triggering large-scale, abrupt, or irreversible environmental changes.

SUMMARY

Mapping ecosystem integrity is a key task of the planetary-boundaries framework. Two new control variables have been suggested for the core planetary boundary for functional biosphere integrity: (1) human appropriation of net primary production (HANPP) and (2) a metric for ecological disruption (EcoRisk). However they have not yet been mapped spatially and temporally explicitly. Here, we use simulations with the dynamic global vegetation model LPJmL to map the status of these variables at a spatial resolution of $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ for every year since 1600. We additionally quantify local degradation thresholds by comparison with independent biosphere integrity indicators. We finally aggregate results globally to a planetary boundary status as the land area transgressing the local thresholds. We find that the local boundary is currently transgressed on 60% of the global land area, with 38% already at high risk of degradation. This study provides an important first step and opens the opportunity for further research, especially for finding a planetary-scale threshold.

INTRODUCTION

The planetary-boundaries framework aims to define environmental limits within which humanity can safely operate. Breaching these boundaries increases the risk of triggering large-scale,

abrupt, or irreversible environmental changes that could destabilize Earth's systems. Biosphere integrity and climate change are identified as "core boundaries."^{1–3} This reflects their dominant role in determining the state and functioning of the Earth system as a whole and their strong interactions with multiple other

boundaries. Limiting their current transgression is key to maintaining the Earth system's state and protecting humanity against planetary-scale change of a magnitude that has no analog in historical experience.⁴ The current major crisis of the coupled climate-biosphere system threatens both the ability of global ecosystems to function and co-regulate Earth's state, and nature's contributions to people,⁵ as documented by a number of indicators discussed, e.g., in a review by Purvis et al.⁶ Maintaining the complex ecological assemblage of organisms that form the biosphere is an essential contribution to safeguarding or re-establishing the globally relatively stable conditions on Earth experienced since the beginning of the Holocene 11,700 years ago, now being disrupted by humanity.^{7,8}

Although strongly interconnected, the two planetary core boundaries reflect substantially different types of change processes co-determining the state of Earth. Although the climate change boundary addresses a central component of the abiotic dimensions of the Earth system, the biosphere integrity boundary addresses the more complex biotic realm of life and ecosystems as a planetary phenomenon. While the planetary boundary for climate change is measured by the globally well-mixed atmospheric CO₂ concentration and change in the overall radiation balance of Earth, the planetary boundary for biosphere integrity has to reflect locally and regionally differentiated, intricate, and ecosystem-specific change processes.^{2,3}

The biosphere-integrity planetary boundary is subdivided into two components: genetic diversity and functional biosphere integrity, each representing a distinct aspect of Earth's ecological functioning.² These components are interconnected, as the survival of existing genetic diversity supports species' ability to maintain ecosystems, while functional integrity addresses the ability of these ecosystems to function as systems, including functioning as a co-regulator of Earth system state.³ We focus here on functional biosphere integrity.

Previous assessments of functional biosphere integrity in the planetary boundaries and the related Earth system boundaries frameworks were based largely on empirical analysis of various indicators of ecosystem state,^{2,9} employing the biodiversity intactness index¹⁰ or minimum natural area requirements to safeguard nature's contribution to regulating the planetary state and/or its contribution to people.¹¹ However, incorporating metrics such as species richness, extinction rate, or genetic composition cannot readily be integrated into Earth system models, while a measure based on minimum natural area requirements is insensitive to internal changes in both natural area (due to climate change) and human managed land (e.g., due to agricultural intensity changes). Neither of these approaches is computable, which impedes the analysis of future scenarios of the coupled human-Earth system as is required for projecting the evolution of planetary-boundaries transgression and for analyzing options for advancing the goals of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Mace et al.¹² suggest to instead investigate control variables for functional diversity that capture enough of the relationship between ecosystem structure and functions, enhanced by biome specific integrity indicators.

In their recent update of the planetary-boundaries framework, Richardson et al.³ therefore propose a new control variable for the functional biosphere integrity boundary, selected to highlight

the dependence of the biosphere on primary production (to complement existing empirical indicators of biodiversity) and to allow for the first time its computation in Earth system models configured as planetary-boundaries simulators. The new definition is based on the premise that the ability of the biosphere to sustain Earth system functions fundamentally depends on the availability of exergy (i.e., energy available to do work). The total exergy available to the biosphere to effectuate its functions is almost exclusively produced by autotrophs through the process of photosynthesis and is subsequently utilized also by heterotrophs along trophic chains.¹³ A more readily quantifiable, computable proxy for this energy flow is the net primary production (NPP) of vegetation, as it not only represents an essential biodiversity variable for ecological functioning¹⁴ but also correlates to some degree with biodiversity at the field scale¹⁵ and beyond.^{16,17} While this correlation does not hold universally at much larger scales (ecoregion to global) due to modulations with temperature,¹⁸ limitation in water or soil nutrients,¹⁹ and forest cover,²⁰ NPP is foundational for the maintenance, growth, and reproduction of the ecosystems that form the biosphere, their networks and internal complexities, and therefore their functions with respect to the Earth system as a whole.²¹

One approach to quantify the degree to which humans modify the NPP available to ecosystems is the human appropriation of NPP (HANPP),²² which is suggested as a control variable for functional biosphere integrity by Richardson et al.³ HANPP summarizes both the direct biomass extraction component for harvested crops, residues, and timber and the indirect NPP change component as a result of human land use. These two components of HANPP are summed and expressed as a fraction of the reference NPP.²³ When HANPP is expressed as a fraction of the (Holocene-equivalent) preindustrial baseline NPP, we write it as HANPP^{Hol}.

Employing HANPP as a planetary boundary has been proposed several times^{24,25} but without providing a full spatio-temporal analysis. Haberl et al.²⁶ argue that "HANPP is a good candidate for an aggregate pressure indicator for biodiversity loss." It is positively correlated with the ecological footprint,²⁷ while species richness decreases with increasing HANPP.²⁸ The species-energy hypothesis^{29–31} supports the assumption that "an increase in HANPP leads to a reduction in biodiversity, or at least exerts a pressure in this direction."³² A recent global species-energy modeling study identifies HANPP as a driver of vertebrate species richness loss.¹⁵ Empirically, in a study for Europe, the relationship is more nuanced, with HANPP being a strong predictor for amphibian species richness loss, especially in southern Europe.³³ Canelas and Pereira³⁴ note that the effects of HANPP on ecosystem functioning are highly context dependent and that more biodiverse land-use systems might be able to cope with substantial biomass extractions.

Additionally, Richardson et al.³ suggest that a more comprehensive representation of the functional biosphere integrity boundary should be complemented by an ecological metric, measuring concurrent changes in vegetation, as well as in key biogeochemical stocks and flows of carbon, water, and nitrogen as driven by primary production. This allows the additional assessment of biosphere integrity as the resulting complex "ecosystem structure, function and composition," determined

by their climatic-geophysical environment to function as a planetary system.³⁵

One such metric is EcoRisk (risk of ecosystem destabilization), measuring biogeochemical and vegetation structural changes,²³ representing ecosystem function and ecosystem structure as essential variable classes of ecosystems.¹⁴ The EcoRisk metric is given as a dissimilarity score between 0 and 1 based on normalized changes in flows and stocks of water, carbon, and nitrogen, as well as vegetation structure, measured between two system states (e.g., different locations, or the same cell at different time steps, or in-between scenarios). Water storage is represented by average annual root-zone soil moisture, carbon, and nitrogen storage by the average annual pools in vegetation and soils. Water, carbon, and nitrogen fluxes are represented by the total in- and out-fluxes of a grid cell per year. Vegetation structure is characterized by the relative share of different plant functional strategies.²³ Heyder et al.³⁶ argue in support of such a metric, that “substantial changes in either basic biogeochemical properties or vegetation composition are likely to imply far-reaching, potentially self-amplifying transformations in the underlying system characteristics, food chains and species composition.”

While Richardson et al.³ focused on a globally aggregated (planetary) boundary for functional biosphere integrity, a spatially and temporally explicit mapping of the two proposed complementary control variables HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk is currently missing. Additionally, thresholds are required to translate the local control variable status into risk levels in the planetary boundary operating space and aggregate local values to biome or global values.

Here, we assess the status of the planetary boundary for functional biosphere integrity based on the biosphere metrics HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk. To do so, we map their local, spatially explicit status on a grid, based on simulations with the dynamic global vegetation model Lund-Potsdam-Jena managed Land (LPJmL).^{37–39} LPJmL calculates climate- and soil-dependent spatially explicit NPP values to compute HANPP^{Hol}, as well as the distribution of vegetation and biogeochemical state variables for fluxes and pools of carbon, nitrogen, and water to compute EcoRisk (for more details see methods: LPJmL). Furthermore, we use independent biosphere integrity data to determine local boundary thresholds for HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk. Aggregating local transgressions to the planetary scale, we find that, today, more than half (60%) of the global land area has transgressed the local boundary, with 38% in the high-risk zone. This study provides an important first step and opens the opportunity for further research (especially for finding a planetary-scale threshold), as is needed also for other planetary boundaries.⁴⁰

RESULTS

Global patterns of the control variables over time

We map the control variables HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk for four different time periods (centered on 1850, 1900, 1950, and 2000), to analyze the historical progression of the patterns (Figure 1).

For these periods in the past, the values of both indicators strongly reflect the presence or absence of cropland. At around 1850, the main areas with high indicator values were Europe, India, China, and the eastern US, where agriculture had been

prominent for a long time. During the late 19th and in the 20th century, land use expanded considerably and, accordingly, HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk mirror this development, showing increasingly high values in ever-larger areas. Particularly after 1900, a strong increase in EcoRisk values emerges, most likely as a result of multiple drivers and simultaneous changes in several of its components (Figure 2B; for more details about the calculation of EcoRisk components see also methods: biospheremetrics). These drivers include the increasing use of nitrogen fertilizer in the mid-20th century as a feature of the Green Revolution but also ongoing conversion from areas with natural vegetation to cropland, which strongly affects nitrogen dynamics even without fertilizer use. These developments reflect substantial increases in the demand for agricultural products due to a rapidly increasing world population as well as the increasing consumption caused by rising *per capita* economic wealth in many world regions. Additionally, after 1950 regions without land use (hence with zero HANPP^{Hol} values) also show EcoRisk values of up to 0.5 (e.g., high-latitude pan-Arctic regions and high-altitude regions like the Tibetan Plateau). This parallel trend indicates the onset of anthropogenic climate change and its impacts on ecosystems (e.g., via increasing N deposition, warming, precipitation change effects and CO₂ fertilization).

Thresholds and precautionary distance

To convert the control variable status into risk levels in the planetary boundary operating space, thresholds are required that mark the boundaries between a safe operating space, a (risky) increasing risk, and a (dangerous) high-risk zone. We derive local thresholds through a comparison with external biosphere integrity indicators using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves.

In the context of the present spatially explicit study of control variables for functional biosphere integrity, local thresholds define the transition from intact to degraded systems. Ideally, these would be derived based on the strict findings of an established generalized, systemic ecological theory of ecosystem functions. However, despite an extensive literature on elements of such a theory and availability of case studies for particular ecosystems, no such general theory currently exists. Therefore, any biosphere integrity metric based on computable proxies like NPP and other biogeochemical variables must, for now, follow two principles: limits must be inferred from relevant ecological data, and boundaries must be set with a precautionary margin to account for uncertainty. This method is common in other fields, such as setting toxicological limits in health or frameworks for insuring complex risks. Similarly, the Paris climate targets reflect precaution under uncertainty, based on scientific risk assessments.

Richardson et al.³ set the threshold for transgressing from safe to increasing risk for a globally aggregated HANPP-based indicator at 10% of the preindustrial NPP, and at 20% for the high-risk zone. This was based on the precautionary principle and the negative trends of numerous indicators suggesting that the high-risk zone has already been entered (see chapter 2.2 in Brondizio et al.⁴¹). In our simulations, 10% were reached (i.e., the planetary boundary crossed) around the year 1900 and 20% around 1990 (Figure 2A). The time around 1900 coincides with considerable land-use expansion in North America and

Figure 1. LPJmL-based average control variable status maps

(A–D) HANPP^{Hol} status (HANPP expressed as fraction of static preindustrial baseline NPP) and (E–H) EcoRisk score (unitless, between 0 and 1), both displayed for four different 30-year time periods centered on 1850, 1900, 1950, and 2000, respectively, all relative to a potential natural reference state. Different color scales are used for HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk, since they have different sensitivities.

Central Eurasia as documented by Klein Goldewijk et al.⁴² (also see Figure 1). From around 1990 onwards, widespread degradation of the biosphere as a result of further accelerated land-use intensity to sustain the consumption of a growing world population becomes clearly visible in other globally aggregated biosphere integrity indicators.⁴³ However, the question remains: what is a threshold of tolerable HANPP at the local level?

Ideally, a local HANPP threshold should be grounded in ecology; i.e., how much NPP is required to sustain key ecosystem functions (pollination, pest regulation, sediment retention, soil microbiota, and critical soil functions). However, values obtained this way are landscape specific and thus different for cropping systems, pastures, or managed forests. Additionally, they are potentially also management specific (e.g., irrigation, fertiliza-

tion, tillage, or more complex settings such as agro-forestry). Such analysis would go beyond the scope of this manuscript. Therefore, our approach is to find local thresholds for both HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk that can be applied everywhere.

Augmenting the provisional analysis in Stenzel et al.²³ (Figures B3, B4, and B7), which suggested a degradation threshold of 0.5 for EcoRisk, we developed a new methodology employing ROC curves (see methods: setting thresholds) to quantify local thresholds for both HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk. For this, the transgression patterns are compared with other biosphere integrity indicators from independent sources including the Biosphere Intactness Index and the Earth System Boundary control variable for functional biosphere integrity (full list in Table S1; for details see methods: external biosphere

Figure 2. Globally aggregated control variable values

(A) $HANPP^{Hol}$ (with range depending on calculation method) over time with biomass harvest components ($NPP_{harvest}$) and inhibited biomass production caused by land-use changes (LUCs) and management practices (NPP_{LUC}), in relation to potential NPP in the reference period 1550–1579. The upper end of range results from aggregating absolute local values (negatives become positive), while for the lower end negative values are kept negative. The previously suggested global boundary threshold values of 0.1 and 0.2 and when they were reached are highlighted with black dotted lines.

(B) EcoRisk (blue) as the average of its components local change (red), global importance (green), ecosystem balance (purple), and vegetation structure change (orange) evaluated for every year based on the 30-year period before compared to the same reference period as for $HANPP^{Hol}$.

integrity indicators for evaluation). Each of these independent biosphere integrity indicators have already defined thresholds (Table S1), which serve as a baseline to determine thresholds of $HANPP^{Hol}$ and EcoRisk.

We use the area under the curve (AUC) measure as a goodness-of-fit measure (minimum value = 0.5, maximum value = 1), where high values indicate high agreement between two indicators. According to this, $HANPP^{Hol}$ and EcoRisk both exhibit good agreement with independent biosphere integrity indicators (Figure 3), despite being completely based on general biogeochemical principles. The AUC values are especially high (> 0.75) for the indicators Human Footprint Index (HFI), Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII), mean species abundance (MSA), contextual intactness (CI), Earth system boundary (ESB), Human Modification Index (HMI), and Biodiversity Habitat Index (BHI). Human-induced soil degradation (GLASOD), Forest Landscape Integrity Index (FLII), and Convergence of Evidence (CoE) (full details in methods: external biosphere integrity metrics and Table S1) show lower AUC values between 0.65 and 0.75 (Figure 3). According to Carter et al.,⁴⁴ optimal thresholds for $HANPP^{Hol}$ and EcoRisk can be obtained, where the difference between the curves for true positives (TP) and false positives (FP) is maximal. The range of optimal thresholds for best agreement with independent biosphere integrity indicators is 0.05–0.58 for $HANPP^{Hol}$ and 0.35–0.66 for EcoRisk. Most of the values fall into the much smaller range of 0.14–0.33 for $HANPP^{Hol}$ and 0.52–0.6 for EcoRisk (except CoE, ESB, and BII). In order to

avoid bias from outliers and obtain robust results, we choose the median as the best estimate for thresholds: 0.23 for $HANPP^{Hol}$ and 0.55 for EcoRisk. Both of these values are in line with earlier estimates.^{3,23} The preliminary threshold for EcoRisk had previously been evaluated to 0.5, while the (albeit global) threshold to the high-risk zone for a globally aggregated $HANPP$ was set to 0.2.

The safe operating space defined by EcoRisk and $HANPP^{Hol}$ requires keeping a cautionary distance from the thresholds, transgression of which may have strong adverse effects. We suggest provisional ranges for the uncertainty/increasing-risk zone based on the lower range of thresholds obtained from the ROC curves of 0.05–0.23 for $HANPP^{Hol}$ and 0.35–0.55 for EcoRisk. The lower end of the range can be interpreted as the value, for which significant degradation occurs according to at least one external independent dataset.

Combined indicator maps and aggregation to global value

Employing the derived thresholds, we combine $HANPP^{Hol}$ and EcoRisk to one local boundary control variable by defining a grid cell to be at increasing or high risk if at least one indicator suggests so (increasing risk, >0.35 for EcoRisk or >0.05 for $HANPP^{Hol}$; high risk, >0.55 for EcoRisk or >0.23 for $HANPP^{Hol}$). The grid-cell-based local boundary is presently transgressed in almost all areas that underwent strong land-cover conversion (due mainly to agriculture), especially in Europe, Asia, and North America (Figure 4).

The results can be aggregated to regional, biome, continental, or global level via the percentage of transgressed area, similar to the approach adopted for the planetary boundary for freshwater change.⁵⁶ In 1900, more than one-third (37%) of the global land area has transgressed the local boundary, with 14% already in the high-risk zone (Figure 5). Today, more than half (60%) of the global land area has transgressed the local boundary, with

Figure 3. Obtaining local boundary thresholds using ROC curves

(A and B) ROC curves assessing optimal thresholds for EcoRisk and HANPP^{Hol} states (average 1987–2016) when comparing with degraded cells according to other biosphere integrity datasets. The curves plot the true-positive (TP) fraction (indicating agreement) against the false-positive (FP) fraction (indicating disagreement) for each possible threshold between 0 and 1 in steps of 0.01. Optimal thresholds can be found where $TP - FP$ is maximal. This might be seen graphically as the point on the curve that is furthest away from the diagonal line $y = x$. Note that the optimal threshold cannot be read directly on the x axis, but is read from the index of the TP-FP pair (see Figure 6).

(C and D) Boxplots of the optimal threshold values across all indicators.

(E and F) Boxplots of area under the curve (AUC) across all indicators. Here, values higher than 0.75 are considered a good fit and values below 0.7 are regarded as poor fit. GLASOD, human-induced soil degradation⁴⁵; HFI, human footprint⁴⁶; BII, biodiversity intactness index^{10,47}; MSA, mean species abundance⁴⁸; FLII, Forest Landscape Intactness Index⁴⁹; CI, contextual intactness⁵⁰; CoE, Convergence of Evidence from World Atlas of Desertification⁵¹; ESB, Earth System Boundary for functional biosphere integrity^{9,11}; HMI, Human Modification Index⁵²; BHI, Biodiversity Habitat Intactness^{53,54}; full details in methods and Table S1.

38% in the high-risk zone. According to the BII, an even larger area is degraded (value <90): 76%. Aggregating the transgressed area per biome shows that both the historical timing as well as the absolute area with transgressions differ strongly between biomes (Figure S3). Biomes in the temperate zone already show large areas with transgressions in 1600, which increases up to 100% of the area today. In all biomes, there is a visible acceleration during the 20th century.

DISCUSSION

To assess functional biosphere integrity in the planetary-boundaries framework, control variables need to be mapped and thresholds derived to translate the local control variable status into risk levels in the planetary boundary operating space and aggregate local values to biome or global values.

(legend on next page)

We provide a spatially and temporally explicit model-based mapping of a newly proposed planetary boundary for functional biosphere integrity based on the computable metrics HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk that represent two pillars for biosphere integrity: (1) maintaining ecosystem-available NPP and (2) stable biogeochemical conditions and vegetation structure. Both constitute essential preconditions for ecosystems to effectively regulate and co-determine the state of the Earth system, consistent with the Holocene baseline, which has governed since the end of the last ice age. Based on rigid comparison with a number of global datasets addressing a variety of biospheric features, we evaluate how representative these metrics are for overall biosphere integrity loss and suggest boundary values accounting for different risk levels. In doing so, we set boundaries based on this evaluation, also applying a precautionary approach to reflect scientific uncertainty in defining and justifying the boundary values as well as the need to sufficiently avoid existential risks of biosphere degradation in view of such uncertainty. Our analysis provides global status maps and time series of the globally aggregated boundary status. We find that, currently, more than half of the global land surface already transgresses the newly proposed boundary for functional biosphere integrity, worryingly congruent with other indicators of ecosystem degradation. The computability and spatial explicitness of this planetary boundary control variable facilitates the construction of planetary boundary simulators based on Earth system models and allows it to be included as an optimization constraint in future sustainability scenarios.

In the following, we discuss further steps toward assessing a planetary status as well as limitations of our approach and outline its potential future application.

While we aggregated the local status to the global area transgressing the local boundaries, the next step toward a truly planetary boundary would be to define a threshold also on the globally aggregated level (e.g., a limit for the global area transgressing the local boundaries). According to Mace et al.,¹² this boundary threshold could be based on the analysis of ecosystem-response variables testing different levels of the control variable. Another avenue could be to focus on specific thresholds on the ecosystem, biome, or continent level. For regions that already have undergone destabilization (i.e., ecosystems already degraded), the threshold when this happened could be determined based on the timing of degradation. Future research could also assess the relevance of the distribution of local transgression across a region: does it make a difference for ecosystem stability, whether small areas are transgressed by wide margins (e.g., due to intensive agriculture) to avoid transgressions in other areas, or whether moderate transgressions could be accepted across large areas? This could imply that areas with high control variable status values within an ecoregion, biome, or continent could be “compensated” by areas with low values.

There are different ways of aggregating HANPP^{Hol} from grid cell to regional or global level, since values can be negative if actual

NPP is higher than potential NPP (see methods: biospheremetrics). 68% of current cell-level transgressions of HANPP^{Hol} are mainly caused by a reduction in NPP ($NPP_{LUC} > NPP_{harvest}$) due to transformation of natural to cultivated land (e.g., via deforestation of primeval forest). Avoiding further transgressions in scenarios aimed at returning us into the safe operating space turns the attention to agricultural intensification on already managed land to increase NPP. Allowing for negative values of HANPP^{Hol} when NPP on managed land is higher than on natural land (through irrigation and fertilization) when aggregating HANPP^{Hol} would suggest that high-intensity management could reduce the overall pressure on the biosphere. On the other hand, summing up absolute HANPP^{Hol} values (i.e., assuming that an increased NPP above the natural NPP would also correspond to a negative effect on biosphere integrity, similar to a decrease in NPP) would imply that high-intensity management is not suitable to reduce the pressure on HANPP^{Hol}.

The methodology developed here using ROC curves could possibly be applied to other planetary boundaries in order to strengthen quantitative threshold setting. For example, it might be applied to the boundaries for biogeochemical flows (especially to regional P) and also to freshwater change (both green and blue). For both, the proposed thresholds could be validated or tested by comparing to the relevant ecological datasets showing degradation.

The used independent biosphere integrity metrics are the best data and reference points currently available. However, there are limitations regarding their use (and associated thresholds indicating severe transgression) as independent ground truth. Most indicators are rather a result of modeling and not pure empirical evidence. In the absence of such observation-based spatially explicit global data on biosphere integrity, caution is advised not to over-interpret the explanatory power of the independent biosphere integrity indicators. Additionally, most of the associated degradation thresholds are not based on biophysical considerations either since drawing clear boundaries based on stringent biophysical considerations is not straightforward. It is thus also important to note that the obtained “optimal” thresholds for HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk require further corroboration. Nevertheless, pending better datasets and thresholds, our approach provides a framework to easily include more indicators or directly measured data in the future.

The planetary-boundaries framework emphasizes that safe boundaries are set in order to quantify the maximum level of human pressures that the Earth system can buffer, without drifting dangerously away from Holocene-like conditions. However, 8 billion people are now inhabiting the planet, whose basic needs need to be sustained.⁵⁷ Thus, one key task is to find alternative Earth system states in the Anthropocene that still allow well-being for both humans and nature.⁵⁸ Good stewardship, e.g., through biodiversity-friendly and environmentally friendly practices such as more sustainable agriculture, can have large

Figure 4. Provisional planetary boundary status maps

Based on (A) only HANPP^{Hol} (average 1987–2016 status) with the zone of uncertainty (increasing risk) defined between > 0.05 and < 0.23 and high risk above > 0.23 , (B) only EcoRisk (average 1987–2016 status) using thresholds with the zone of uncertainty (increasing risk) defined between > 0.35 and < 0.55 and high risk above > 0.55 , and (C) both indicators combined, applying the maximum status that at least one of the indicators has. While (A) and (B) are continuous, (C) is a discrete scale, with three colors handpicked from the safe, uncertainty, and high-risk zones. For a map that also shows where one or both indicators are transgressed, see Figure S5. The maps have been generated with the *boundaries* software package⁵⁵ (<https://github.com/pik-tess/boundaries>).

Figure 5. Global area with transgression of local boundaries of HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk combined: HANPP^{Hol} (boundary, 0.05; high-risk zone, 0.23) and EcoRisk (0.35; 0.55)

The intermediate- and high-risk status is assigned if at least one of the two thresholds is crossed. For the high-risk status, we display a confidence interval as the Q25–Q75 threshold ranges (HANPP^{Hol}, 0.18–0.32; EcoRisk, 0.54–0.59). For time series of HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk individually, see Figure S2. Biome-specific area transgressed is shown in Figure S3. Global land area: 14,900 Mha.

positive effects on biosphere integrity.^{59–61} However, it remains to be studied whether this is compatible with lesser transgression of the planetary boundary as measured by the new change metrics used herein, since food security is not a central goal of the planetary boundaries, rather the safe and just earth system boundaries. Additionally, as suggested by the Earth Commission, critical natural ecosystems need to be kept intact or restored to protect biodiversity functions.⁶² This requires land prioritization for nature on several spatial scales.⁹ The control variables EcoRisk and HANPP^{Hol} used here can only capture a fraction of this, partially because of missing biophysical processes in the LPJmL model (such as use of pesticides and introduction of invasive species) and the relatively coarse resolution.

We were able to map the transgression patterns for a 0.5° × 0.5° resolution, although model improvements (and comparisons) are still needed to firmly establish our metrics as a new definition for the planetary-boundaries framework. This includes a better representation of landscape patterns, which may play a big role in ecology (e.g., edge effects, landscape diversity, small-scale heterogeneity), an improved ecological rationale for threshold setting, and a well-founded way to derive a global planetary threshold from the spatial pattern. On the path toward such a scientific foundation of a planetary boundary for functional biosphere integrity, the spatial mapping of the two computable metrics presented here is an important next step but also highlights the challenges still on the agenda concerning the second major pillar of planetary stability next to climate, biosphere integrity.

METHODS

Biospheremetrics

In our analysis, we make use of the biospheremetrics software package (Stenzel et al.²³ and <https://github.com/stenzelf/biospheremetrics>) to compute two biosphere integrity indicators.

HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk are based on simulations with the dynamic global vegetation model LPJmL. Both HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk metrics use as their benchmark a baseline of preindustrial natural conditions computed with potential natural vegetation absent of human land use and climate as well as CO₂ representative of preindustrial conditions (for more details see methods: simulation protocol).

HANPP^{Hol} quantifies the human appropriation of net primary production (HANPP²²) with respect to the Holocene NPP and

is computed via the indicator BioCol from the biospheremetrics package.²³ To highlight the connection to HANPP, we do not use the name BioCol in this paper, although it is identical to HANPP^{Hol}. HANPP indicates that humanity appropriates about one-quarter of the global potential NPP,⁶³ and this impact has doubled during the 20th century,^{64,65} thereby substantially decreasing the NPP remaining in ecosystems. The two components of HANPP are the flow of biomass (in terms of NPP; see Figure S4 for a comparison with remotely sensed NPP from MODIS^{66,67}) that is intentionally extracted through crop, residue, and biomass harvests ($NPP_{harvest}$) and the inhibited biomass production caused by land-use changes and management practices (NPP_{LUC}). NPP_{LUC} is calculated as the difference between the potential natural NPP (NPP_{pot}), which represents biomass production without land use, and the actual biomass production (NPP_{act}), both under the same climate.

$$NPP_{LUC} = NPP_{pot} - NPP_{act} \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

NPP_{LUC} can become negative if the actual NPP is higher than potential NPP (e.g., through management or land-use legacy effects, especially on managed grasslands).

The absolute HANPP is calculated as the sum of NPP_{LUC} and $NPP_{harvest}$.

$$HANPP = NPP_{LUC} + NPP_{harvest} \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

HANPP^{Hol} is then computed as the ratio of absolute HANPP to a reference baseline NPP (NPP_{ref}), in this case the (Holocene equivalent) undisturbed preindustrial NPP_{pot} . We use a superscript “Hol” to indicate a reference change, while subscripts for HANPP denote the components.

$$HANPP^{Hol} = HANPP / NPP_{ref} \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

The preindustrial terrestrial potential NPP levels were stable with 63 ± 2 GtC/year, slightly above the range of earlier estimates of Holocene potential NPP of 52–62 GtC/year.^{68–70}

To aggregate local HANPP^{Hol} values from grid cell to regional or global level, we first sum up the local HANPP and NPP in terms of carbon and obtain the aggregated HANPP^{Hol} by dividing these values. There are, however, three different ways to aggregate, since HANPP grid-cell values can be negative if actual NPP is higher than potential NPP ($NPP_{act} > NPP_{pot}$) and biomass harvests are low.

Keeping negative values leads to the lowest aggregated numbers. Taking the absolute of all grid-cell values, on the other hand, leads to the highest numbers. For aggregating HANPP^{Hol} to the global level, we chose the intermediate way by setting negative HANPP^{Hol} grid-cell values to zero, which leads to a global sum of 22.5% of preindustrial NPP for the latest period, in the middle of the range from 21% to 24% given by Stenzel et al.²³ and re-plotted in Figure 2A.

EcoRisk is based on the ecosystem change metric Γ ³⁶ and illustrates state shifts of ecosystems as a result of land use and climate change. Using a scale ranging from 0 (no change) to 1 (very strong change), this metric quantifies the dissimilarity of an ecosystem state from the preindustrial reference. It accounts for shifts in the vegetation structure (e.g., transition of forest to savanna), as well as relative (relevant for the local scale) and absolute shifts (relevant for the global scale) in soil and vegetation carbon stocks and fluxes, nitrogen stocks and fluxes, and changes in the water cycle. EcoRisk comprises four sub-components (vegetation structure [vs], local change [lc], global importance [gi], ecosystem balance [eb]) that are aggregated as a proxy for the risk of biosphere destabilization, each on the same scale of 0–1 and internally scaled with the respective (reference state) change-to-variability ratio $S(x, \sigma_x)$, following⁷¹

$$\begin{aligned} \text{EcoRisk} &= \frac{vs+lc+gi+eb}{4} \\ &= \frac{V \cdot S(V, \sigma_V) + l \cdot S(l, \sigma_l) + g \cdot S(g, \sigma_g) + e \cdot S(e, \sigma_e)}{4} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

Vegetation structural changes are computed based on the differences in plant distribution for both natural and managed areas,^{72,73} while the other three components are based on different normalizations of the difference between the local and the baseline multidimensional state vectors, all based on outputs by LPJmL.

For the unscaled vegetation structure component V , LPJmL provides outputs of the ground area covered by natural and cultivated plant types. Changes in vegetation structure are computed between ecosystem state i and j with respect to the total area (G) of ground cover type (GCT) k (tree, grass, or barren), further detailed by the differences between the plant functional type (PFT) (ρ) specific area (A) regarding attribute l (evergreenness, needleleavedness, tropicalness, borealness, naturalness). For PFT specific attributes (a) see Table 2 in Stenzel et al.²³ Barren is defined without subcategories. The attribute specific weighting factor ω_{kl} is per default set to 0.2 (=“equal” weighting). Alternatively, attribute specific weights as in⁷¹ can be applied.

$$\begin{aligned} V(i, j) &= 1 - \sum_k \left\{ \underbrace{\min(G_{ik}, G_{jk})}_{\text{total area of GCT } k} \cdot \left[1 - \sum_l \left(\omega_{kl} \left| \underbrace{\sum_p (A_{iklp} \cdot a_{klp}) - \sum_p (A_{jklp} \cdot a_{klp})}_{\text{specific area difference regarding attribute } l} \right| \right) \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Equation 5})$$

The remaining unscaled components l , g , and e are computed from two ecosystem state vectors \vec{s}_1 (reference state) and \vec{s}_2 (changed state), composed of 30-year averages of biogeochemical variables $v_{i,1}$ and $v_{i,2}$, with $i = [1, \dots, n]$.

$$\vec{s}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} v_{1,1} \\ \vdots \\ v_{n,1} \end{pmatrix}, \vec{s}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} v_{1,2} \\ \vdots \\ v_{n,2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{Equation 6})$$

They represent the major process cycles on the grid-cell level determining plant growth: carbon, nitrogen, and water. While there are separate planetary boundaries covering nitrogen input into the biosphere and changes in the water cycle, these variables are also important for ecosystem function. Local changes in nitrogen, carbon, and water variables and the vegetation composition can indicate a risk for a decline in ecosystem function. The system described by the metric is the terrestrial land system, which has pools as well as in- and out-fluxes across the system boundary. For carbon and nitrogen, stocks are aggregated into a vegetation and soil pool, for water there is only a soil pool. In total, this gives 11 dimensions, plus one dimension reserved for other relevant processes, which for LPJmL is filled with the fire fraction (see Table 3 in Stenzel et al.²³).

The components l and g are now computed as the length of the difference vector between the two state vectors after applying different normalizations. For local change l , the state variables are normalized with the local values of the reference state, indicating how strongly the local conditions have changed in relative terms. Global importance g , in contrast, puts local changes in perspective to the global mean reference condition, taking into account that even moderate changes on the local scale may feed back to larger scales if large enough in absolute terms. Therefore, the state vectors are normalized with the global, spatially averaged reference mean value of each variable.

Ecosystem balance e quantifies shifts in the relative magnitude of biogeochemical properties with respect to each other as an indicator for qualitative changes in the balance of dynamic processes, which may signal a breakdown of ecological functioning.⁷¹ It is calculated from the angle between the two state vectors with local normalization (as for local change).

The Γ metric has been used to compare the relative importance of climate warming and land-use change as historical drivers of ecosystem change⁷³ or to derive temperature thresholds above which climate change is expected to cause severe ecosystem change with high probability.⁷⁴

Compared to the original definition of Γ ³⁶, later adapted by Ostberg et al.⁷³ to measure the effects of land-use change, EcoRisk includes nitrogen fluxes and pools. Additionally, some of the original state variables describing ecosystems (fluxes and pools) in previous applications have been changed (for more details see Stenzel et al.²³).

External biosphere integrity indicators for evaluation

In this section and the associated Table S1, we list the external biosphere integrity datasets used for validation and threshold setting (methods, setting thresholds) of HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk. All indicators are plotted in Figure S1.

GLASOD is an expert-based world map for type, degree, and causal factors of human-induced soil degradation.⁴⁵

The HFI is a measure of human influence on terrestrial ecosystems across the globe integrating population density, land transformation (including crop and pasture lands), accessibility (major roadways, railways, and navigable waterways), electrical power infrastructure (measured by light pollution), and built environment.⁴⁶

The BII quantifies the impact of human activities on biodiversity by how much of an ecosystem's original biodiversity remains intact in the face of human pressures, particularly land-use changes.¹⁰

GLOBIO 4 projects terrestrial biodiversity intactness using MSA, based on several key components: land-use changes, climate-change impacts, habitat fragmentation, nitrogen pollution, and hunting impacts in tropical regions.⁴⁸

The FLII is a global measure of forest condition based on the degree of anthropogenic modification using satellite imagery and other data to evaluate forest integrity on a continuous scale.⁴⁹

The CI is a global biodiversity conservation metric that evaluates habitats based on their relative ecological value compared to biologically similar regions by identifying areas that serve as critical refuges for species using the HFI.⁵⁰

The CoE metric is a methodological framework used in the third edition of the World Atlas of Desertification (WAD3) to identify areas at risk of land degradation by synthesizing multiple global datasets with an emphasis on overlapping stressors.⁵¹

The safe and just ESB for functional biosphere integrity focuses on maintaining the ecological functions of human-modified ecosystems at a landscape scale and requires at least 20%–25% diverse seminatural habitat, including native species, in each square kilometer of human-modified lands.^{9,11}

The HMI is a global metric designed to quantify the degree to which terrestrial ecosystems have been altered by human activities (spatial extent and intensity) across landscapes.⁵²

The BHI is a measure that estimates the impacts of habitat loss, degradation, and fragmentation on terrestrial biodiversity using remotely sensed forest change and land-cover-change datasets.⁵³

LPJmL

The ecosystem data used for the analysis is generated with the dynamic global vegetation model LPJmL 5.7.^{37–39} It simulates essential ecological and physiological processes such as photosynthesis and respiration, as well as dependent carbon, water, and nitrogen dynamics for natural ecosystems and on managed land, and has been extensively validated^{38,39,75} (see Figure S4 for a comparison with remotely sensed NPP from MODIS^{66,67}). The simulations are based on historical records of land use, soil properties, nitrogen inputs, and climate variables. Natural vegetation is represented by 11 plant functional types whose abundance is influenced by climatic parameters, growth efficiency, competition, and fire disturbance.⁷⁶ Agricultural vegetation is modeled through the most abundant 12 crop functional types,⁷⁷ and grassland/pastures.⁷⁸ Other crops are simulated as either temperate wheat or tropical maize, depending on their geographic location (latitude). The model dynamically calculates optimal sowing dates for crop functional types, which are fixed

after the year 2000.⁷⁹ The model routes local runoff through a global network of water bodies and rivers as accumulated discharge.⁸⁰ While irrigated crop area is prescribed, irrigation needs and associated water withdrawals are dynamically computed based on soil water deficit and available renewable water resources in lakes, rivers, reservoirs, and adjacent cells.⁸¹ LPJmL also simulates various agricultural management practices, including tillage, manure, fertilizer application, and the optional growth of off-season cover crops.^{82,83} The model tracks carbon, nitrogen, and water fluxes and stocks at a spatial resolution of $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ and a daily timescale, with all outputs aggregated annually for this study.

Simulation protocol

For this study, we ran LPJmL 5.7 with GSWP3-W5E5 climate data from the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP), which combines daily Global Soil Wetness Project Phase 3 (GSWP3) data (1901–1978) with a bias-adjusted version of the reanalysis climate dataset ERA5 from 1979 to 2016, called W5E5 (adjusted to better match the datasets from the Climatic Research Unit and the Global Precipitation Climatology Centre).^{84,85} Prior to 1901, climate inputs are randomly recycled from the first 30 years of available data. Data on manure, fertilizer, and crop areas from 1500 to 2017 are taken from a new hybrid dataset.⁸⁶ Fallow lands are categorized under the “others” crop class, and the disaggregation into different irrigation systems follows Jägermeyr et al.⁸¹ Livestock densities on grasslands are prescribed,⁸⁷ estimated based on grazing levels in 2000 at regional and production system scales.^{88,89} Tillage practices are based on Lutz et al. and Porwollik et al.^{82,90}

To calculate EcoRisk and HANPP^{Hol}, the functions provided by the biospheremetrics software package, described in Stenzel et al.,²³ are used. This software utilizes the R package lpjmlkit⁹¹ for reading LPJmL outputs. The metrics are computed based on two LPJmL simulations: one with historical land use and one without (potential natural). HANPP^{Hol} is computed annually in comparison to the average preindustrial period 1550–1579 from the potential natural simulation. EcoRisk is computed in comparison to the same 30-year reference time period, with a moving 30-year analysis window (1586–1615 until 1987–2016).

Local boundary status maps are created using the boundaries software package (<https://github.com/pik-tess/boundaries>).

Setting thresholds

To quantitatively assess optimal thresholds for EcoRisk and HANPP^{Hol} indicating a high risk for biosphere integrity loss, we compare their average state of 1987–2016 against 10 other biosphere integrity indicators (full list in section external biosphere integrity indicators for evaluation and Table S1). The method we chose for the comparison are ROC curves,^{92–94} which are based on comparing binary values for each grid cell: degraded or not degraded (Figure 6). For the independent biosphere integrity dataset this classification is fixed; for our datasets HANPP^{Hol} and EcoRisk, we systematically vary the degradation threshold between 0 and 1 in steps of 0.01, thus creating different splits of our datasets. For each threshold, we obtain the areas for which both agree (TP, blue) and for which our metric indicates degradation, but the independent dataset does not (FP, red). Both areas are normalized with the respective maximum

Figure 6. Scheme depicting the method for determining an optimal boundary threshold, based on ROC curves and comparison with other biosphere integrity datasets

The control variable map (shown here is EcoRisk; the same methodology applies to HANPP^{total}) for average 1987–2016 is transformed from the continuous scale to a binary, using all possible thresholds between 0 and 1 in steps of 0.01 (we show this example for 0.2 and 0.8). Binary EcoRisk and binary independent degradation status are compared to yield the areas for which both agree (true-positive [TP] fraction, blue) and for which EcoRisk indicates degradation, but the independent dataset does not (false positive [FP], red). The normalized areas are plotted against every threshold in the lower left. The ROC curve (bottom right) plots TP against FP. The larger the area under the curve (AUC) is, the better is the agreement between the two indicators. We find the optimal threshold (denoted in green), where the difference between TP and FP is maximal.

area. The optimal thresholds can then be found where the difference between TP and FP (green) is maximal, which is similar to the point of optimal sensitivity and specificity.⁴⁴ Graphically, this is the point furthest from the diagonal line $y = x$. Additionally, we compute the AUC, by point-wise summation of rectangles with height $TP(x)$ and width $FP(x_{i+1}) - FP(x_i)$. The AUC is a measure of similarity between the two datasets. The closer the value is to 1, the better is their performance to explain each other.⁹³

In order to avoid bias from outliers and obtain robust results, we chose the median among the different thresholds as the best estimate for the high-risk thresholds. According to the pre-

cautionary principle, we set the local boundary threshold to the minimum of the obtained thresholds.

RESOURCE AVAILABILITY

Lead contact

Further information and requests for resources and materials should be directed to the lead contact, Fabian Stenzel (stenzel@pik-potsdam.de).

Materials availability

Data generated in this study have been deposited to Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15806793>.

Annual maps and timelines of aggregated control-variable status are additionally made available on this website <https://biointegrty.pik-potsdam.de/>, with the source-code deposited to Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15869840>).

Data and code availability

All original code has been deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15806793>) and is publicly available as of the date of publication.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank Thomas Harwood for providing an aggregated BHI map and discussing potential thresholds, Aafke Schipper for discussing potential thresholds, and Julia Jünger for proofreading. We thank the Ecosystems in Transition group at PIK and especially Boris Sakschewski for fruitful discussions. This research has been supported by the Global Challenges Foundation through the Future Earth project fund “New Governance Architecture for Addressing Global Systemic Risks” and the FORMAS project ReForMit. H.H. acknowledges funding for the MAT_STOCKS project, grant agreement no. 741950, by the European Research Council, as well as funding for the REMASS project by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), 10.55776/EF5. K.E., S.M., and N.R. are funded by the Austrian Science Fund project “LandCube” (P 35420-G). J. Braun’s contribution is part of the Planetary Boundaries Science Lab’s research effort at PIK, which is funded by The Grantham Foundation for the Protection of the Environment. The authors gratefully acknowledge the Ministry of Research, Science and Culture (MWFK) of Land Brandenburg for supporting this project by providing resources on the high performance computer system at the Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research. We thank Steve Running, two anonymous reviewers, and the editor for their valuable comments.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

F.S., conceptualization, methodology, software, validation, formal analysis, writing – original draft, and visualization; L.B.U., methodology (ROC curves) and writing – review & editing; J. Braun, methodology, software, and writing – review & editing; J. Breier, software and writing – review & editing; K.E., methodology and writing – review & editing; D.G., writing – review & editing and supervision; S.M., methodology, data curation, and writing – review & editing; R. M., methodology (ROC curves) and writing – review & editing; H.H., methodology and writing – review & editing; S.O., methodology, software, and writing – review & editing; J.R., writing – review & editing; N.R., methodology and writing – review & editing; S.S., data curation and writing – review & editing; W.L., conceptualization, writing – review & editing, supervision, and funding acquisition.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

SUPPLEMENTAL INFORMATION

Supplemental information can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2025.101393>.

Received: October 11, 2024

Revised: April 30, 2025

Accepted: July 11, 2025

Published: August 15, 2025

REFERENCES

- Rockström, J., Steffen, W., Noone, K., Persson, Å., Chapin, F.S., Lambin, E.F., Lenton, T.M., Scheffer, M., Folke, C., Schellnhuber, H.J., et al. (2009). A safe operating space for humanity. *Nature* 461, 472–475. <https://doi.org/10.1038/461472a>.
- Steffen, W., Richardson, K., Rockström, J., Cornell, S.E., Fetzer, I., Bennett, E.M., Biggs, R., Carpenter, S.R., Vries, W.d., Wit, C.A.d., et al. (2015). Planetary boundaries: Guiding human development on a changing planet. *Science* 347, 1259855. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1259855>.
- Richardson, K., Steffen, W., Lucht, W., Bendtsen, J., Cornell, S.E., Donges, J.F., Drüke, M., Fetzer, I., Bala, G., von Bloh, W., et al. (2023). Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries. *Sci. Adv.* 9, eadh2458. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adh2458>.
- Ripple, W.J., Wolf, C., Gregg, J.W., Rockström, J., Mann, M.E., Oreskes, N., Lenton, T.M., Rahmstorf, S., Newsome, T.M., Xu, C., et al. (2024). The 2024 state of the climate report: Perilous times on planet earth. *Bioscience* 74, 812–824. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae087>.
- Pörtner, H.O., Scholes, R.J., Arnett, A., Barnes, D.K.A., Burrows, M.T., Diamond, S.E., Duarte, C.M., Kiessling, W., Leadley, P., Managi, S., et al. (2023). Overcoming the coupled climate and biodiversity crises and their societal impacts. *Science* 380, eabl4881. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abl4881>.
- Purvis, A., Molnár, Z., Obura, D., Ichii, K., Willis, K., Chettri, N., Dulloo, M., Hendry, A., Gabrielyan, B., Gutt, J., et al. (2019). Chapter 2.2. status and trends – nature. In *Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services*, pp. 202–309. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5517457>.
- Crutzen, P.J. (2002). Geology of mankind. *Nature* 415, 23. <https://doi.org/10.1038/415023a>.
- Zalasiewicz, J., Williams, M., Haywood, A., and Ellis, M. (2011). The anthropocene: a new epoch of geological time? *Philos. Trans. A Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* 369, 835–841. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2010.0339>.
- Rockström, J., Gupta, J., Qin, D., Lade, S.J., Abrams, J.F., Andersen, L.S., Armstrong McKay, D.I., Bai, X., Bala, G., Bunn, S.E., et al. (2023). Safe and just Earth system boundaries. *Nature* 619, 102–111. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06083-8>.
- Newbold, T., Hudson, L.N., Arnell, A.P., Contu, S., De Palma, A., Ferrier, S., Hill, S.L.L., Hoskins, A.J., Lysenko, I., Phillips, H.R.P., et al. (2016). Has land use pushed terrestrial biodiversity beyond the planetary boundary? a global assessment. *Science* 353, 288–291. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaf2201>.
- Mohamed, A., DeClerck, F., Verburg, P.H., Obura, D., Abrams, J.F., Zafra-Calvo, N., Rocha, J., Estrada-Carmona, N., Fremier, A., Jones, S.K., et al. (2024). Securing Nature’s Contributions to People requires at least 20%–25% (semi-)natural habitat in human-modified landscapes. *One Earth* 7, 59–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2023.12.008>.
- Mace, G.M., Reyers, B., Alkemade, R., Biggs, R., Chapin, F.S., Cornell, S.E., Díaz, S., Jennings, S., Leadley, P., Mumby, P.J., et al. (2014). Approaches to defining a planetary boundary for biodiversity. *Glob. Environ. Change* 28, 289–297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.07.009>.
- Jorgensen, S.E., and Svirezhev, Y.M. (2004). *Towards a Thermodynamic Theory for Ecological Systems* (Elsevier).
- Pereira, H.M., Ferrier, S., Walters, M., Geller, G.N., Jongman, R.H.G., Scholes, R.J., Bruford, M.W., Brummitt, N., Butchart, S.H.M., Cardoso, A.C., et al. (2013). Essential biodiversity variables. *Science* 339, 277–278. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1229931>.
- Reiter, K., Plutzer, C., Moser, D., Semenchuk, P., Erb, K.H., Essl, F., Gattringer, A., Haberl, H., Krausmann, F., Lenzen, B., et al. (2023). Human appropriation of net primary production as driver of change in landscape-scale vertebrate richness. *Glob. Ecol. Biogeogr.* 32, 855–866. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.13671>.
- Gillman, L.N., Wright, S.D., Cusens, J., McBride, P.D., Malhi, Y., and Whittaker, R.J. (2015). Latitude, productivity and species richness. *Global Ecol. Biogeogr.* 24, 107–117. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12245>.
- Cusens, J., Wright, S.D., McBride, P.D., and Gillman, L.N. (2012). What is the form of the productivity–animal-species-richness relationship? A critical review and meta-analysis. *Ecology* 93, 2241–2252. <https://doi.org/10.1890/11-1861.1>.

18. Costanza, R., Fisher, B., Mulder, K., Liu, S., and Christopher, T. (2007). Biodiversity and ecosystem services: A multi-scale empirical study of the relationship between species richness and net primary production. *Ecol. Econ.* 61, 478–491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2006.03.021>.
19. Huston, M.A. (2012). Precipitation, soils, NPP, and biodiversity: resurrection of Albrecht's curve. *Ecol. Monogr.* 82, 277–296. <https://doi.org/10.1890/11-1927.1>.
20. Marull, J., Tello, E., Bagaria, G., Font, X., Cattaneo, C., and Pino, J. (2018). Exploring the links between social metabolism and biodiversity distribution across landscape gradients: A regional-scale contribution to the land-sharing versus land-sparing debate. *Sci. Total Environ.* 619–620, 1272–1285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.11.196>.
21. Díaz, S. (2013). Ecosystem function measurement, terrestrial communities. In *Encyclopedia of Biodiversity*, Second Edition, S.A. Levin, ed. (Academic Press), pp. 72–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-384719-5.00042-3>.
22. Haberl, H., Erb, K.H., Krausmann, F., and Lucht, W. (2004). Defining the human appropriation of net primary production. *LUCS Newsl.* 10, 16–17.
23. Stenzel, F., Braun, J., Breier, J., Erb, K., Gerten, D., Heinke, J., Matej, S., Ostberg, S., Schaphoff, S., and Lucht, W. (2024). biospheremetrics v1.0.2: an r package to calculate two complementary terrestrial biosphere integrity indicators – human colonization of the biosphere (biocol) and risk of ecosystem destabilization (ecorisk). *Geosci. Model Dev. (GMD)* 17, 3235–3258. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-17-3235-2024>.
24. Running, S.W. (2012). A measurable planetary boundary for the biosphere. *Science* 337, 1458–1459. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1227620>.
25. Haberl, H., Erb, K.H., and Krausmann, F. (2014). Human appropriation of net primary production: Patterns, trends, and planetary boundaries. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* 39, 363–391. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-121912-094620>.
26. Haberl, H., Erb, K.H., Plutzer, C., Fischer-Kowalski, M., and Krausmann, F. (2012). Human appropriation of net primary production (hanpp) as an indicator for pressures on biodiversity. In *Sustainability indicators: a scientific assessment* chap. 17, T. Håk, B. Moldan, and A.L. Dahl, eds. (Island Press), pp. 271–287.
27. Vačkář, D. (2012). Ecological Footprint, environmental performance and biodiversity: A cross-national comparison. *Ecol. Indic.* 16, 40–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2011.08.008>.
28. Haberl, H., Wackernagel, M., Krausmann, F., Erb, K.H., and Monfreda, C. (2004). Ecological footprints and human appropriation of net primary production: a comparison. *Land Use Policy* 21, 279–288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2003.10.008>.
29. Vitousek, P.M., Ehrlich, P.R., Ehrlich, A.H., and Matson, P.A. (1986). Human appropriation of the products of photosynthesis. *Bioscience* 36, 368–373. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1310258>.
30. Wright, D.H. (1983). Species-Energy Theory: An Extension of Species-Area Theory. *Oikos* 41, 496–506. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3544109>.
31. Wright, D.H. (1990). Human impacts on energy flow through natural ecosystems, and implications for species endangerment. *Ambio* 19, 189–194.
32. Plutzer, C., Erb, K.H., Gaube, V., Haberl, H., and Krausmann, F. (2016). Of Birds and Bees: Biodiversity and the Colonization of Ecosystems. In *Social Ecology: Society-Nature Relations across Time and Space*, H. Haberl, M. Fischer-Kowalski, F. Krausmann, and V. Winiwarter, eds. (Springer International Publishing), pp. 375–388. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-33326-7_18.
33. Mouchet, M., Levers, C., Zupan, L., Kuepperle, T., Plutzer, C., Erb, K., Lavorel, S., Thuiller, W., and Haberl, H. (2015). Testing the Effectiveness of Environmental Variables to Explain European Terrestrial Vertebrate Species Richness across Biogeographical Scales. *PLoS One* 10, e0131924. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0131924>.
34. Canelas, J.V., and Pereira, H.M. (2022). Impacts of land-use intensity on ecosystems stability. *Ecol. Model.* 472, 110093. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2022.110093>.
35. Hansen, A.J., Noble, B.P., Veneros, J., East, A., Goetz, S.J., Supples, C., Watson, J.E.M., Jantz, P.A., Pillay, R., Jetz, W., et al. (2021). Toward monitoring forest ecosystem integrity within the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. *Conserv. Lett.* 14, e12822. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12822>.
36. Heyder, U., Schaphoff, S., Gerten, D., and Lucht, W. (2011). Risk of severe climate change impact on the terrestrial biosphere. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 6, 034036. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/6/3/034036>.
37. Schaphoff, S., von Bloh, W., Rammig, A., Thonicke, K., Biemans, H., Forkel, M., Gerten, D., Heinke, J., Jägermeyr, J., Knauer, J., et al. (2018). Lpjml4 – a dynamic global vegetation model with managed land – part 1: Model description. *Geosci. Model Dev. (GMD)* 11, 1343–1375. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-11-1343-2018>.
38. von Bloh, W., Schaphoff, S., Müller, C., Rolinski, S., Waha, K., and Zaehle, S. (2018). Implementing the nitrogen cycle into the dynamic global vegetation, hydrology, and crop growth model lpjml (version 5.0). *Geosci. Model Dev. (GMD)* 11, 2789–2812. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-11-2789-2018>.
39. Wirth, S.B., Braun, J., Heinke, J., Ostberg, S., Rolinski, S., Schaphoff, S., Stenzel, F., von Bloh, W., Taube, F., and Müller, C. (2024). Biological nitrogen fixation of natural and agricultural vegetation simulated with lpjml 5.7.9. *Geosci. Model Dev. (GMD)* 17, 7889–7914. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-17-7889-2024>.
40. Biermann, F., and Kim, R.E. (2020). The boundaries of the planetary boundary framework: A critical appraisal of approaches to define a “safe operating space” for humanity. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* 45, 497–521. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-012320-080337>.
41. Brondizio, E.S., Settele, J., Díaz, S., and Ngo, H.T. (2019). Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3831673>.
42. Klein Goldewijk, K., Beusen, A., Doelman, J., and Stehfest, E. (2017). Anthropogenic land use estimates for the holocene – hyde 3.2. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* 9, 927–953. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-9-927-2017>.
43. Leclère, D., Obersteiner, M., Barrett, M., Butchart, S.H.M., Chaudhary, A., De Palma, A., DeClerck, F.A.J., Di Marco, M., Doelman, J.C., Dürauer, M., et al. (2020). Bending the curve of terrestrial biodiversity needs an integrated strategy. *Nature* 585, 551–556. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2705-y>.
44. Carter, J.V., Pan, J., Rai, S.N., and Galandiuk, S. (2016). ROC-ing along: Evaluation and interpretation of receiver operating characteristic curves. *Surgery* 159, 1638–1645. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surg.2015.12.029>.
45. Oldeman, L.R., Hakkeling, R., and Sombroek, W.G. (1990). *World Map of the Status of Human-Induced Soil Degradation: An Explanatory Note (International Soil Reference and Information Centre)*.
46. Venter, O., Sanderson, E.W., Magrath, A., Allan, J.R., Behr, J., Jones, K.R., Possingham, H.P., Laurance, W.F., Wood, P., Fekete, B.M., et al. (2016). Sixteen years of change in the global terrestrial human footprint and implications for biodiversity conservation. *Nat. Commun.* 7, 12558. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms12558>.
47. De Palma, A., Contu, S., Thomas, G.E., Duffin, C., Nix, S., and Purvis, A. (2024). The biodiversity intactness index developed by the natural history museum, london, v2.1.1 (open access, limited release). *Natural History Museum*. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5519/K33REYB6>.
48. Schipper, A.M., Hilbers, J.P., Meijer, J.R., Antão, L.H., Benítez-López, A., de Jonge, M.M.J., Leemans, L.H., Scheper, E., Alkemade, R., Doelman, J.C., et al. (2020). Projecting terrestrial biodiversity intactness with GLOBIO 4. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 26, 760–771. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14848>.
49. Grantham, H.S., Duncan, A., Evans, T.D., Jones, K.R., Beyer, H.L., Schuster, R., Walston, J., Ray, J.C., Robinson, J.G., Callow, M., et al. (2020). Anthropogenic modification of forests means only 40% of remaining forests have high ecosystem integrity. *Nat. Commun.* 11, 5978. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-19493-3>.
50. Mokany, K., Ferrier, S., Harwood, T.D., Ware, C., Di Marco, M., Grantham, H.S., Venter, O., Hoskins, A.J., and Watson, J.E.M. (2020). Reconciling

- global priorities for conserving biodiversity habitat. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 117, 9906–9911. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1918373117>.
51. Cherlet, M., Hutchinson, C., Reynolds, J., Hill, J., Sommer, S., and Von Maltitz, G.E. (2018). World Atlas of Desertification: Rethinking Land Degradation and Sustainable Land Management (Publication Office of the European Union). <https://doi.org/10.2760/06292>.
 52. Kennedy, C.M., Oakleaf, J.R., Theobald, D.M., Baruch-Mordo, S., and Kiesecker, J. (2019). Managing the middle: A shift in conservation priorities based on the global human modification gradient. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 25, 811–826. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14549>.
 53. Harwood, T., Ware, C., Hoskins, A., Ferrier, S., Bush, A., Golebiewski, M., Hill, S., Ota, N., Perry, J., Purvis, A., and Williams, K. (2022). Bhi V2: Biodiversity Habitat Index: 30s Global Time Series (Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation). <https://doi.org/10.25919/3j75-f539>.
 54. GEO BON (2015). Global Biodiversity Change Indicators. Version 1.2. (Leipzig: Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network Secretariat), p. 20.
 55. Gerten, D., Braun, J., Breier, J., Lucht, W., Tobian, A., and Stenzel, F. (2025). A soft ware package for assessing terrestrial planetary boundaries. *One Earth* 8, 101341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2025.101341>.
 56. Porkka, M., Virkki, V., Wang-Erlandsson, L., Gerten, D., Gleeson, T., Mohan, C., Fetzer, I., Jaramillo, F., Staal, A., te Wierik, S., et al. (2024). Notable shifts beyond pre-industrial streamflow and soil moisture conditions transgress the planetary boundary for freshwater change. *Nat. Water* 2, 262–273. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44221-024-00208-7>.
 57. Gupta, J., Liverman, D., Prodani, K., Aldunce, P., Bai, X., Broadgate, W., Ciobanu, D., Gifford, L., Gordon, C., Hurlbert, M., et al. (2023). Earth system justice needed to identify and live within Earth system boundaries. *Nat. Sustain.* 6, 630–638. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-023-01064-1>.
 58. Rockström, J., Beringer, T., Hole, D., Griscom, B., Mascia, M.B., Folke, C., and Creutzig, F. (2021). We need biosphere stewardship that protects carbon sinks and builds resilience. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 118, e2115218118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2115218118>.
 59. Underwood, T., McCullum-Gomez, C., Harmon, A., and Roberts, S. (2011). Organic Agriculture Supports Biodiversity and Sustainable Food Production. *J. Hunger Environ. Nutr.* 6, 398–423. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19320248.2011.627301>.
 60. Robertson, G.P. (2015). A Sustainable Agriculture? *Daedalus* 144, 76–89. https://doi.org/10.1162/DAED_a_00355.
 61. Cappelli, S.L., Domeignoz-Horta, L.A., Loaiza, V., and Laine, A.L. (2022). Plant biodiversity promotes sustainable agriculture directly and via below-ground effects. *Trends Plant Sci.* 27, 674–687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2022.02.003>.
 62. Gupta, J., Bai, X., Liverman, D.M., Rockström, J., Qin, D., Stewart-Koster, B., Rocha, J.C., Jacobson, L., Abrams, J.F., Andersen, L.S., et al. (2024). A just world on a safe planet: a lancet planetary health–earth commission report on earth-system boundaries, translations, and transformations. *Lancet Planet. Health* 8, e813–e873. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(24\)00042-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(24)00042-1).
 63. Haberl, H., Erb, K.H., Krausmann, F., Gaube, V., Bondeau, A., Plutzer, C., Gingrich, S., Lucht, W., and Fischer-Kowalski, M. (2007). Quantifying and mapping the human appropriation of net primary production in earth's terrestrial ecosystems. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 104, 12942–12947. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0704243104>.
 64. Krausmann, F., Erb, K.H., Gingrich, S., Haberl, H., Bondeau, A., Gaube, V., Lauk, C., Plutzer, C., and Searchinger, T.D. (2013). Global human appropriation of net primary production doubled in the 20th century. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 110, 10324–10329. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1211349110>.
 65. Kastner, T., Matej, S., Forrest, M., Gingrich, S., Haberl, H., Hickler, T., Krausmann, F., Lasslop, G., Niedertscheider, M., Plutzer, C., et al. (2022). Land use intensification increasingly drives the spatiotemporal patterns of the global human appropriation of net primary production in the last century. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 28, 307–322. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15932>.
 66. Running, S.W., and Zhao, M. User's guide daily gpp and annual npp (mod17a2h/a3h) and year-end gap-filled (mod17a2hgf/a3hgf) products nasa earth observing system modis land algorithm (for collection 6). Tech. Rep. MODIS Land Team (2019). URL: <https://modis-land.gsfc.nasa.gov/pdf/MOD17C61UsersGuideV11Mar112021.pdf>. accessed: 2025-05-12.
 67. Kern, S. (2024). MODIS Collection 6.1 global yearly gap-filled Gross and Net Primary Production. <https://doi.org/10.25592/uhhfdm.14635>.
 68. Foley, J.A. (1994). The sensitivity of the terrestrial biosphere to climatic change: A simulation of the Middle Holocene. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycles* 8, 505–525. <https://doi.org/10.1029/94GB01636>.
 69. Brovkin, V., Bendtsen, J., Claussen, M., Ganopolski, A., Kubatzki, C., Petoukhov, V., and Andreev, A. (2002). Carbon cycle, vegetation, and climate dynamics in the Holocene: Experiments with the CLIMBER-2 model. *Glob. Biogeochem. Cycles* 16, 86–1. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2001GB001662>.
 70. Smith, B., Wårlind, D., Armeth, A., Hickler, T., Leadley, P., Siltberg, J., and Zaehle, S. (2014). Implications of incorporating n cycling and n limitations on primary production in an individual-based dynamic vegetation model. *Biogeosciences* 11, 2027–2054. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-2027-2014>.
 71. Ostberg, S., Boysen, L.R., Schaphoff, S., Lucht, W., and Gerten, D. (2018). The biosphere under potential paris outcomes. *Earths Future* 6, 23–39. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017EF000628>.
 72. Sykes, M.T., Prentice, I.C., and Laarif, F. (1999). Quantifying the impact of global climate change on potential natural vegetation. *Clim. Change* 47, 37–52. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1005435831549>.
 73. Ostberg, S., Schaphoff, S., Lucht, W., and Gerten, D. (2015). Three centuries of dual pressure from land use and climate change on the biosphere. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 10, 044011. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/10/4/044011>.
 74. Ostberg, S., Lucht, W., Schaphoff, S., and Gerten, D. (2013). Critical impacts of global warming on land ecosystems. *Earth Syst. Dyn.* 4, 347–357. <https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-4-347-2013>.
 75. Schaphoff, S., Forkel, M., Müller, C., Knauer, J., von Bloh, W., Gerten, D., Jägermeyr, J., Lucht, W., Rammig, A., Thonicke, K., and Waha, K. (2018). LPJmL4 – a dynamic global vegetation model with managed land: Part II – model evaluation. *Geosci. Model Dev. Discuss. (GMDD)* 2018, 1–41. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-2017-146>.
 76. Sitch, S., Smith, B., Prentice, I.C., Armeth, A., Bondeau, A., Cramer, W., Kaplan, J.O., Levis, S., Lucht, W., Sykes, M.T., et al. (2003). Evaluation of ecosystem dynamics, plant geography and terrestrial carbon cycling in the LPJ dynamic global vegetation model. *Glob. Change Biol.* 9, 161–185. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2486.2003.00569.x>.
 77. Bondeau, A., Smith, P.C., Zaehle, S., Schaphoff, S., Lucht, W., Cramer, W., Gerten, D., Lotze-Campen, H., Müller, C., Reichstein, M., and Smith, B. (2007). Modelling the role of agriculture for the 20th century global terrestrial carbon balance. *Glob. Change Biol.* 13, 679–706. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2006.01305.x>.
 78. Heinke, J., Rolinski, S., and Müller, C. (2023). Modelling the role of livestock grazing in c and n cycling in grasslands with lpjml5.0-grazing. *Geosci. Model Dev. (GMD)* 16, 2455–2475. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-2455-2023>.
 79. Waha, K., van Bussel, L.G.J., Müller, C., and Bondeau, A. (2012). Climate-driven simulation of global crop sowing dates. *Global Ecol. Biogeogr.* 21, 247–259. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-8238.2011.00678.x>.
 80. Gerten, D., Schaphoff, S., Haberlandt, U., Lucht, W., and Sitch, S. (2004). Terrestrial vegetation and water balance—hydrological evaluation of a dynamic global vegetation model. *J. Hydrol.* 286, 249–270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2003.09.029>.
 81. Jägermeyr, J., Gerten, D., Heinke, J., Schaphoff, S., Kumm, M., and Lucht, W. (2015). Water savings potentials of irrigation systems: global simulation of processes and linkages. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 19, 3073–3091. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-19-3073-2015>.

82. Lutz, F., Herzfeld, T., Heinke, J., Rolinski, S., Schaphoff, S., von Bloh, W., Stoorvogel, J.J., and Müller, C. (2019). Simulating the effect of tillage practices with the global ecosystem model Ipjml (version 5.0-tillage). *Geosci. Model Dev. (GMD)* *12*, 2419–2440. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-2419-2019>.
83. Porwollik, V., Rolinski, S., Heinke, J., von Bloh, W., Schaphoff, S., and Müller, C. (2022). The role of cover crops for cropland soil carbon, nitrogen leaching, and agricultural yields – a global simulation study with Ipjml (v. 5.0-tillage-cc). *Biogeosciences* *19*, 957–977. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-19-957-2022>.
84. Kim, H. (2017). Global soil wetness project phase 3 (gswp3) - atmospheric boundary conditionsdoi: <https://doi.org/10.20783/DIAS.501>.
85. Lange, S. (2019). WFDE5 over land merged with ERA5 over the ocean (W5E5). v. 1.0. GFZ Data Services. <https://doi.org/10.5880/pik.2019.023>.
86. Ostberg, S., Müller, C., Heinke, J., and Schaphoff, S. (2023). Landing 1.0: a toolbox to derive input datasets for terrestrial ecosystem modelling at variable resolutions from heterogeneous sources. *Geosci. Model Dev. (GMD)* *16*, 3375–3406. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-3375-2023>.
87. Heinke, J. (2025). A livestock density input for LPJmL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14946695>.
88. Herrero, M., Havlík, P., Valin, H., Notenbaert, A., Rufino, M.C., Thornton, P. K., Blümmel, M., Weiss, F., Grace, D., and Obersteiner, M. (2013). Biomass use, production, feed efficiencies, and greenhouse gas emissions from global livestock systems. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* *110*, 20888–20893. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1308149110>.
89. Heinke, J., Lannerstad, M., Gerten, D., Havlík, P., Herrero, M., Notenbaert, A.M.O., Hoff, H., and Müller, C. (2020). Water Use in Global Livestock Production—Opportunities and Constraints for Increasing Water Productivity. *Water Resour. Res.* *56*, e2019WR026995. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019WR026995>.
90. Porwollik, V., Rolinski, S., Heinke, J., and Müller, C. (2019). Generating a rule-based global gridded tillage dataset. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* *11*, 823–843. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-11-823-2019>.
91. Breier, J., Ostberg, S., Wirth, S.B., Hötten, D., Minoli, S., Stenzel, F., and Müller, C. (2024). Ipjmlkit: A toolkit for operating LPJmL and model-specific data processing. *J. Open Source Softw.* *9*, 5447. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.05447>.
92. Vermont, J., Bosson, J.L., François, P., Robert, C., Rueff, A., and Demongeot, J. (1991). Strategies for graphical threshold determination. *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.* *35*, 141–150. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-2607\(91\)90072-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-2607(91)90072-2).
93. Fawcett, T. (2006). An introduction to ROC analysis. *Pattern Recognit. Lett.* *27*, 861–874. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patrec.2005.10.010>.
94. Peres, D.J., and Cancelliere, A. (2014). Derivation and evaluation of landslide-triggering thresholds by a monte carlo approach. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* *18*, 4913–4931. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-18-4913-2014>.